

MICROBIAL DEGRADATION OF EFFLUENT FROM BERGER AREA ABATTOIR AT LAGOS/ OGUN STATE BOUNDARY NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Maintenance of proper hygiene and adequate sanitary conditions is an issue of concern in an abattoir. This research work is centered on how abattoir effluent can be treated using microorganisms before releasing it into the environment especially water body to ameliorate environmental pollution. In the light of the above, two of the three genera that showed complete hemolytic ability from the screening test carried out on all bacterial isolates from abattoir samples (water, soil and sediment) were selected for use in abattoir effluent degradation. The genera are *Streptococcus* and *Bacillus*. A general pattern was observed in the abattoir effluent degradation using *Streptococcus* and *Bacillus* species in isolation and combination, carried out for duration of three weeks. It is observed generally that the Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD) and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) reduced in the first two weeks of the degradation process and started picking again at the third week of the exercise. The total suspended solid (TSS) was increasing throughout the duration of the investigation while the total dissolved solid (TDS) was reducing. It is the sum of TSS and TDS that gives the total solid (TS). The reduction in BOD and COD in the first two weeks (14 days) is indication of reduction in pollution level of the abattoir effluent and the rising in value of BOD and COD at third week of the investigation (21 days) is also an indication that the microbial communities were getting old (Prescott *et. al.*, 2008). The total suspended solid was increasing throughout the experiment as a result of production of new biomass. Also the total dissolved solid was reducing throughout the experiment because organisms are using it to supply energy for their own metabolic processes and production of biomass.

Key words: Abattoir, Effluent, Degradation, Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), Total Solid (TS)

INTRODUCTION

The most important issue in all meat-processing plants is maintenance of proper hygiene and adequate sanitary conditions. An abattoir has been defined as a premise approved and registered by the controlling authority for hygienic slaughtering and inspection of animals, processing and effective preservation and storage of meat products for human consumption [1]. Abattoir waste can be defined as waste or

waste water from an abattoir which could consist of the pollutants such as animal faeces, blood, fat, animal trimmings, paunch content and urine [2].

[3] observed that effluent discharged from slaughterhouses has caused the deoxygenation of rivers. Effluent from slaughterhouses has also been known to contaminate ground water [4]. [5] also showed that the pollution potential of meat processing and slaughter-house plants has been

estimated at over one million population equivalent in the Netherlands. [6] reported during a study in Germany that blood, one of the major dissolved pollutants in slaughter effluent, has a chemical oxygen demand (COD) of 375,000 mg/l. This impacts high organic pollutants on receiving waters consequently creating high competition for oxygen within the ecosystem. This chemical oxygen demand value is far higher than the maximum limit of 80 mg/l set by [7] / [8] In Nigeria, Abattoirs are frequently located near urban centers and enormous amounts of wastes are produced in relatively small areas. In most abattoirs in Nigeria, the waste from the abattoir operations is a source of embarrassment as conventional methods for the disposal of animal wastes, carcasses and manure, as well as slaughterhouse and other animal industry wastes are now proving inadequate in Nigeria [2].

Ongoing production quality control, washing and disinfection, are the main procedures of securing the hygiene of meat and meat products [9],[10]. In the production of animal for food, more attention should be focused on the interactions between animal production and the environment, realizing environmental conditions and structures in animal production, which not only seek to produce wholesome and safe animal food but should also avoid environmental pollution and the associated human health risks.

Environmental problems have increased in geometric proportion over the last three decades with improper abattoir management practices being largely responsible for the gross pollution of the aquatic environment with concomitant increase in water borne diseases especially typhoid, diarrhea and dysentery. Abattoirs are generally known all over the world to pollute the environment either directly or indirectly from their various processes [2]. [4] have also investigated the pollution load of effluent from four abattoirs at Ibadan, and found that all other parameters such as biological oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), total solids(TS), total dissolved solid(TDS) and total suspended solid(TSD) except pH were higher

than the permissible limits set by national and international regulatory bodies.

This research analysis looks at microbial degradation of effluent from Berger Area abattoir at Lagos/ Ogun state boundary Nigeria. That is, how abattoir effluent can be treated using microorganisms before releasing it into the environment especially water bodies to ameliorate environmental pollution.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Standard methods were used throughout the course of this analysis. Having established in the introduction that many abattoirs in Nigeria release myriads of untreated wastes into the environment especially abattoir effluent into water bodies. The study site of this research work is no exception. Abattoir effluent can be treated using microorganisms before releasing it into the environment especially water bodies to ameliorate environmental pollution. In the light of the above, two of the three genera that showed complete hemolytic ability from the screening test carried out on all bacterial isolates were selected for use in abattoir effluent degradation process. The genera are *Streptococcus* and *Bacillus*. These were grown in nutrient broth for 4 days at 37°C and cell / ml was determined by plate count method (8×10^7 cells per ml was used). The genera were used singly and in combined form for the effluent degradation. 10mls of the grown culture broth was introduced into 200ml each of unsterile and sterile effluents. Control experiments of unsterile and sterile effluents with and without sterile broth (10mls) were also set up. (There are four controls and six treatments in all).

Parameters such as Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), Total suspended solid (TSS), Total dissolved solid (TDS) and Total solid (TS) were determined for control at zero day and also for controls and treatments at seven days intervals for three weeks.

Hemolytic test

This test was carried out as screening for bacterial isolates to determine isolate's hemolytic ability and to properly select bacteria isolates that will be used in the degradation of abattoir effluent. Blood agar was prepared by evenly mixing 5ml of fresh uncoagulated blood with 100ml of sterile Nutrient agar. Bacteria isolates were streaked on solidified blood agar and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Complete clear zone around line of streak indicates complete hemolysis known as Beta hemolysis. Incomplete clear zone indicate partial hemolysis known as alpha hemolysis. No clear zone around line of streak is termed as negative result.

Biochemical Oxygen Demand

This measures the total amount of oxygen needed by microorganisms to completely oxidized organic matter in a treated sample. The principle of this method is based on the determination of the dissolved oxygen content of the liquid before and after incubation for five days at 20°C. The value of dissolved oxygen was taken for 200ml of four control samples on day 1. The 200ml of each control sample was put in BOD bottles and incubated in the dark at 20°C for five days after which the dissolved oxygen content was determined. The BOD of each control sample was determined using the formula below and result expressed as milligram/litre (mg/l). The same procedure was used for BOD determination for controls and treated effluent samples on day 7, 14 and 21.

Calculation:

$$\text{BOD (mg/l)} = (\text{DO1} - \text{DO5}) - (\text{B1} - \text{B5}) / \text{P}$$

DO1= Dissolved oxygen in sample for day 1

DO5 = Dissolved oxygen in sample for day 5

B1= Dissolved oxygen in Blank (dilution sample only) for day 1

B5 = Dissolved oxygen in Blank (dilution sample only) for day 5

P = Decimal volumetric fraction of the sample use.

$$\text{P} = 1 / \text{F}$$

F= Dilution factor = Total volume/ Volume of sample.

Chemical Oxygen Demand

This is a measure of the total amount of oxygen which is required to completely oxidize all the organic matter in a treated sample. The principle of this method is based on refluxing, digestion and titration of both the sample and blank. The Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) of controls and treated abattoir effluent was determined through refluxing, digestion and titration of both the sample and blank. The result is expressed as milligram/litre (mg/l).

Calculation:

$$\text{COD (mg/l)} =$$

$$\frac{(\text{Blank titration} - \text{Sample titration}) \times 1000}{\text{Volume of sample taken (ml)}}$$

Total Suspended Solid

The suspended solid is determined by filtering the sample through filter paper, drying the residue and determining its weight by difference. 100ml of a well mixed sample was filtered through already weighed filter paper and the residue was dried in an oven at 105°C. The dried filter paper containing the residue was then weighed. Total suspended solid is calculated using the formula below and result expressed as milligram/litre (mg/l).

Formula: Total suspended solid (mg/l) =

$$\frac{(\text{W2} - \text{W1}) \text{mg} \times 1000}{\text{Volume of sample (ml)}}$$

W1 is the weight of the filter paper (mg).

W2 is the weight of the dried filter paper containing residue (mg).

Total Dissolved solid

The dissolved solid was obtained by subtracting the value obtained for suspended solid from that obtained for total solid and result expressed as milligram/litre (mg/l) for both controls and treated effluent samples.

Calculation:

Dissolved solid (mg/ l) = Total solid (mg / l) –
Suspended solid (mg / l)

Total Solid

The principle is to evaporate and dry a known volume of a well mixed sample in a weighed dish at 105⁰C to a constant weight. The increase in weight over the empty dish represent total solid. Total solids include Total suspended solids (TSS) and Total Dissolved solids (TDS).

100ml of a well mixed sample in a weighed dish was evaporated at 105⁰C in an oven.

The weight of the evaporating dish was taken at interval until a constant weight was obtained for three times. The final weight of the dish and the content was taken and recorded. The total solid was calculated using the formula below and result expressed as milligram/litre (mg/l).

Formula: Total solid (mg/l) =

$\frac{(W2 - W1)mg \times 1000}{\text{Volume of sample (ml)}}$

Volume of sample (ml)

W1 is the weight of the dish (mg).

W2 is the weight of the dish of dried residue (mg).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effluents from the meat industry, abattoir in particular are highly polluting in nature. Such effluents typically contain large amounts of suspended and dissolved nitrogenous organic materials as well as emulsified fats and greases. In order to meet the water quality standards required by current environmental regulations it is necessary to treat such effluents to remove the bulk of the pollutant load. Organic materials in abattoir effluents are usually of a readily biodegradable nature and consequently biological methods of treatment have traditionally been used for such wastes. Thus in the meat industry methods based on lagooning and more recently on the activated sludge and trickle filtration processes have become popular. The underlying principle of such systems is that the organic materials in the effluent are degraded

by a large stable population of microorganisms. The organisms use the material for two purposes, firstly to supply energy for their own metabolic processes and secondly to produce new organisms. Thus the net result of the degradation of the pollutants in the effluents is the generation of waste gases such as carbon monoxide as a result of metabolic activity and the production of new biomass. Excess quantities of such biomass are produced to some degree in all biological waste treatment systems. This material is wasted from the system as sludge with high water content, the disposal of which can pose serious problems, but the sludge can be utilized in various useful possible ways.

In relation to the brief description of effluents from meat works or abattoirs and the underlying principle of degradation, a similar pattern was observed in the abattoir effluent degradation investigation using *Streptococcus* and *Bacillus species* in isolation and combination, carried out for duration of three weeks (Fig-1). It was observed generally that the Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD) and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) reduced in the first two weeks of the degradation process and started picking again at third week of the investigation. The total suspended solid (TSS) was increasing throughout the duration of the experiment while the total dissolved solid (TDS) was reducing. It is the sum of TSS and TDS that gives the total solid (TS).

The reduction in BOD and COD in the first two weeks (14days) is indication of reduction (Table-2 & Fig.1-6) in pollution level of abattoir effluent and the rising in value of BOD and COD at the third week of the investigation (21days) is also an indication that the microbial communities were getting old [11].

The total suspended solid was increasing throughout the experiment as a result of production of new biomass. Also the total dissolved solid was reducing throughout the experiment because organisms are using it to supply energy for their own metabolic processes and production of biomass.

Table 1: Abattoir effluent degradation result at day 0 for controls

CODE	B.O.D	T.S.S	T.D.S	T.S	C.O.D
A	270.17	286.20	61.90	348.10	867.53
B	262.28	378.20	53.65	852.83	852.83
C	246.65	686.45	42.96	799.24	799.94
D	235.53	756.65	38.61	795.26	767.60

All units is in milligram per litre (mg/l).

A- Unsterile control without broth; B- Unsterile control with broth; C- Sterile control without broth; D; Sterile control with broth.

Table 2: Abattoir effluent degradation result for controls and treatments at day 7

CODE	B.O.D.	T.S.S.	T.D.S.	T.S.	C.O.D
A	244.86	484.12	51.82	535.94	764.61
B	240.65	492.50	46.10	538.60	646.98
C	244.95	687.51	40.12	727.63	797.94
D	232.80	757.01	37.61	794.62	764.80
E	186.05	899.10	38.62	937.72	588.16
F	230.17	798.30	30.21	828.51	720.49
G	204.47	588.62	36.21	624.83	623.42
H	225.26	762.21	29.13	791.34	705.79
I	159.07	687.11	28.64	715.75	523.40
J	161.54	918.01	24.12	942.13	514.64

All units is in mg/l

KEY

E	Unsterile effluent with <i>Streptococcus species</i>
F	Sterile effluent with <i>Streptococcus species</i>
G	Unsterile effluent with <i>Bacillus species</i>
H	Sterile effluent with <i>Bacillus species</i>
I	Unsterile effluent with <i>Bacillus + Streptococcus</i>
J	Sterile effluent with <i>Bacillus + Streptococcus</i>

Fig.1.Unsterilized abattoir effluent degradation by *Streptococcus species*

Fig.2.Sterilized abattoir effluent degradation by *Streptococcus species*

Table 3: Abattoir effluent degradation result for controls and treatments at day 14

CODE	B.O.D.	T.S.S.	T.D.S.	T.S.	C.O.D.
A	166.45	526.20	46.21	572.41	529.34
B	141.94	712.13	38.81	750.94	455.82
C	238.55	692.11	39.01	731.12	789.64
D	225.51	746.14	35.02	781.16	756.52
E	132.14	796.51	28.03	824.54	426.42
F	53.72	825.61	22.07	847.68	191.15
G	19.41	669.72	32.61	702.33	88.22
H	141.94	805.61	18.13	823.74	255.82
I	83.13	783.10	23.23	806.33	279.38
J	130.67	982.31	21.61	1003.92	450.02

All units is in mg/l

Table-4: Abattoir effluent degradation result for controls and treatments at day 21

CODE	B.O.D.	T.S.S.	T.D.S.	T.S.	C.O.D.
A	176.84	686.52	39.04	725.56	570.53
B	167.63	778.01	35.01	813.02	552.90
C	240.86	712.20	38.01	750.21	817.57
D	230.80	751.61	34.01	785.62	772.52
E	166.25	812.10	25.12	837.22	558.75
F	161.35	862.17	20.10	882.27	344.05
G	58.42	795.12	30.11	825.23	235.26
H	146.65	828.01	16.03	844.04	399.94
I	156.45	805.10	21.21	826.31	529.34
J	151.55	991.13	20.14	1011.27	514.64

All unit in mg/ l

Fig3.Unsterilized abattoir effluent degradation by *Bacillus species*

Fig-4: Sterilized abattoir effluent degradation by *Bacillus species*

Fig-5:Unsterilized abattoir effluent degradation by *Streptococcus* and *bacillus* species

Fig.6.Sterilized abattoir effluent degradation by *Streptococcus* and *Bacillus* species

REFERENCES

1. Alonge, D. O. (1991) . Textbook of meat hygiene in the tropics Farmcoe press, Ibadan 58pp
2. Adelegan, J.A., 2002. Environmental policy and slaughterhouse waste in Nigeria. Proceedings of the 28th WEDC Conference, Calcutta, India, pp: 3-6.
3. Quinn JM, McFarlane PN(1989). Effect of slaughterhouse and dairy factory effluent on epilithon, Water Res. 23: 1267 – 1273 .
4. Sangodoyin AY, Agbawe OM 1992. Environmental Studyon Surface and Ground Water Pollutants fromAbattoir Effluents. *Bioresource Technology*, 41:193-200.

Elsevier Science publishers Ltd. Great Britain.

5. Sayed SKI(1987). Anaerobic Treatment of slaughterhouse wastewater using UASB process. Ph.D Thesis. Wageningen, The Netherlands: Agricultural University of Wageningen.
6. Tritt, W.P. and F. Schuchardt, 1992. Materials flow and possibilities of treating liquid and solid wastes from slaughterhouses in Germany. *Bioresour. Technol.*, 41 (3): 235-245.63
7. FEPA (Federal Environmental Protection Agency), 1991. National environmental protection regulations (effluent limitation) regulations S.1.8. Federal Republic of Nigeria Official Gazette, No. 42, Vol. 78, Lagos.
8. FMEnv (Federal Ministry of Environment), 2001. National guidelines and standards for water quality in Nigeria, pp: 114.
9. Pezacki, W. (1970). Mikrobiologiczne Problemy Technologii Miesa. *Post. Mikrobiol.* 9 (3), 472-441
10. Windyga, B., Grochowska, A., Urbanek-Kalowska, B. and Napiorkowaka, B. (1996). Preparaty Dezynfekujace Dopuszczone Do Stosowania W. Zacladach Przetworstwa Spozywczego. *Przem. Spoz.* 50 (6), 27-34.
11. Prescott, L.M. Harley, J.P. and Klein, D.A.2008. *Microbiology* 7th edition McGraw Hill New York Pp. G – 30

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